

RADIANT CREATOR

Workshop

“Conservation farming on mountain farms”

19th - 20th September 2024

**Tecnopolo di Reggio Emilia, Reggio Emilia
Castello di Sarzana, Casina, Reggio Emilia, Italia**

**Hosted by CRPA Soc. Cons. p. A
Aurora farm n. 20**

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Executive Summary

The objective of this Radiant Creator Workshop was to consolidate results obtained in Radiant Aurora Farm (AF) #20 along the Parmigiano Reggiano PDO cheese – prodotto di Montagna supply chain: from forage producers to consumers. The objective of AF#20 is to identify underutilised crops (UC) to increase farmers' self-sufficiency of local forages to feed cows for **Parmigiano Reggiano prodotto di Montagna**.

The workshop was organized over two different days (19th and 20th September 2024). The first day was dedicated to consumers, while the second day to farmers, breeders, technicians, etc. The total number of participants was 46. The objective of the workshop was to understand the expectation of value chain actors, critical points, opinions and discuss issues with the production and valorisation of the forages produced within the Parmigiano Reggiano prodotto di montagna value chain.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background and objectives

The objective of Radiant Aurora Farm (AF) #20 is to identify underutilised crops (UC) to increase farmers' self-sufficiency of local forages to feed cows for **Parmigiano Reggiano (PR) prodotto di Montagna**. AF#20 is focused on the identification of alfalfa ecotypes that better adapt to hilly/mountainous conditions and the use of air-dried whole plant legumes (such as *Pisum sativum arvense L.*) intercropped with cereals to improve protein production as well as forage's yields in mountain areas.

To consolidate the results along the PR supply chain the results obtained in Aurora farm 20, CRPA has organised a Radiant Creator workshop for all stakeholders of the value chain PR prodotto di montagna from farmers to consumers. During the two sessions of the workshop, the project was introduced to participants and activities were carried out on the farm. Two focus group were held to understand the view of consumers and farmers, technicians, providers, and researchers on the critical points and strengths associated with the use of underutilised crops in the PR prodotto di montagna value chain. Discussion with the different stakeholders was also useful to identify critical aspects.

In the end, farmers visited the alfalfa comparison field trial and discussed the production results, in terms of total yields and protein yields, dormancy, etc., of the different ecotypes tested.

1.2 Workshop framework and participants

The workshop was organised over 2 days. The first session focussed on consumers and was held in Reggio Emilia to facilitate participation of

consumers from different demographics, who are not used to find this product.

The workshop began with an introduction to the Radiant project and its activities. This was followed by a focus group to understand consumers' behaviour regarding "PR prodotto di montagna" produced with milk from cows fed with selected underutilised crops. At the end, a discussion with consumers allowed strength, weakness, opportunities and threats (SWOT) to be identified.

The second session was dedicated to farmers, farmers' suppliers, researchers and technicians. It was organised in Casina, where the AF#20 is located. This location allowed the participation of farmers from mountains areas, who were given the opportunity to visit the trial fields.

After describing the project objectives and activities to the farmers, a focus group aimed to understand the behaviour of farmers regarding the use of underutilised crops for feeding (sowing, using), a SWOT analysis was performed on the cultivation and use of underutilised crops for Parmigiano Reggiano prodotto di montagna production. The participants then visited the alfalfa comparison trial which was seeded within the Radiant project, and a field where the farmer seed Foxtail millet intercropped with alfalfa.

The total number of consumers in session 1 was 21, whilst 25 farmers attended the second session (Figure 1). The main group of stakeholders in the workshop were Parmigiano Reggiano farmers as well as alfalfa producers. The total number of researchers and technician was 7. Other participants included a representative of Consorzio del Formaggio Parmigiano Reggiano and a journalist (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Overall distribution of the stakeholders, who attended the workshop.

Figure 2. Distribution of the stakeholders, who attended the second session of the workshop.

2. Presentations

2.1 Presentations Overview

The workshop aimed to illustrate and integrate the results obtained in AF 20 along the PR supply chain. The presentations introduced the project, the objectives of the AF and its results (Figure 3A).

The workshop allowed most of the time, in the 2 sessions to the discussion of the SWOT, which allowed the participants to better understand the results, but also provide valuable information for the dissemination and valorisation of the activities carried out (Figure 3B).

Printed copies of the field scheme together with some preliminary results were given to participants to illustrate and better describe the trial (Figure 3C).

Figure 3. **A.** Anna Garavaldi (CRPA) introducing the workshop; **B.** Simone Piras introducing the consumers' focus group; and **C.** Fabrizio Ruozzi during the field visits.

3. Demonstration activity / Field visit

3.1 Visit of Alfalfa cultivar comparison trial

The objective of the demonstrative activity was to demonstrate the differences between different cultivars of alfalfa (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Visit of the the alfalfa comparison trial field.

3.2 Intercropping Foxtail millet + alfalfa field

This part of the visit showcased an example of intercropping, which the farmer sowed to improve yields with an UC (Foxtail millet) during the first year of alfalfa when productions are low (Figure 5).

Figure 5. The Foxtail millet - alfalfa field visit

4. Outputs of focus group discussions

In the framework of **T5.3 “Farmers’ and consumers’ expectations and preferences for UCs”**, the James Hutton Institute implemented focus group discussions with consumers (in Reggio-Emilia on 19 September 2024) and farmers (in Casina on 20 September 2024). Each discussion lasted around 1.5 hours. They started with a survey questionnaire including a **choice experiment** (DCE), followed by a **SWOT analysis** to identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats related to the production and marketing (consumption) of Parmigiano Reggiano obtained with milk from cows fed with underutilised crops. More precisely, the **Research Centre for Animal Productions (CRPA)** identified two **specialised grasslands (mixtures)** to be rotated with alfalfa in the mountainous areas of the Parmigiano Reggiano district, which could increase the resilience and sustainability of mountain agriculture: one containing **gramineous crops**, and one containing **leguminous crops**. The farmers were asked to make the same choices after the SWOT discussion, to assess the impact of increased awareness of UCs’ agroecological benefits on their preferences for the mixtures proposed. Below, we provide a short overview of the results of the questionnaires, and summaries of the discussions.

4.1 Consumers

The **environmental sustainability** was seen as the main strength of introducing underutilised fodder mixtures in the diets of cows whose milk is used to produce Parmigiano. This could also become a unique selling point. In turn, the **lack of information** for ordinary consumers,

who are not necessarily aware of the benefits or do not care about them, was seen as a current weakness. Additionally, the participants mentioned that the Parmigiano **market** is **complex** and quite well **consolidated**, making the introduction of new layers of complexity, including potential labels, risky. The risk is further increased by **uncertainty** in terms of **price**, **taste** and **colour** of the derived products. Therefore, the promotion of UCs within animal productions faces more challenges than when UCs are consumed directly, like in the case of fresh vegetables, as they do not easily result in a price premium.

4.2 Farmers

The **diversity** of local and farm-level conditions were significant, which made drawing general recommendations difficult. For instance, the practices to grow the underutilised mixtures, and their resistance to haymaking procedures, are not homogeneous, not only between mountain and plain areas, but also within these. Additionally, it is important to distinguish between farmers who produce for commercial **sale**, and those who **use** their own fodder.

All the farmers recognised the agroecological and other **benefits** of the underutilised mixtures proposed, including stronger initial **resistance to parasites**, increase in fodder quality, and the possibility to take advantage of **autumn rains** in a context of increasing water scarcity. The potential presence of a sale agreement, linked to a **production prize**, was mentioned as an important opportunity for the uptake of these mixtures.

In turn, introducing further **differentiation** in the Parmigiano Reggiano supply chain was considered difficult, given that there are already a number of additional certifications such as the logo “Mountain Product”, or the use of red cows’ milk. This is a risk, as already shown by the limited success of the “**Mountain Product**” logo in terms of price premium for farmers. Still, the consortium could try and create a **niche**. In this regard, the **small scale of cheese factories** in mountain areas constitutes an opportunity since it would simplify the **coordination** of cows’ nutrition among the farmers supplying the milk. This step is essential to ensure the cows are fed in a specific way, paving the way for a corresponding logo for retail consumers.

For more information on the results of the discussion, please see D5.3 Farmers and consumers preferences and behavioural economics underpinning UC choice currently under preparation.

Annex I - Program

RADIANT CREATOR WORKSHOP SESSIONE CONSUMATORI PROGRAM

19 Settembre 2024

Tecnopolo di Reggio Emilia, (RE), Italia

Piazzale Europa 1 – Reggio Emilia (RE)

RADIANT - *Realizing Dynamic Value Chains for Underutilised Crops* - è un progetto europeo del programma H2020 coordinato dalla Universidade Católica Portuguesa di Porto (Portogallo) che coinvolge 29 enti di 12 Paesi. Il suo obiettivo è quello di sfruttare al meglio il valore delle colture e della loro diversità genetica per renderle più competitive e rafforzare le strategie dell'UE per filiere agroalimentari sostenibili, e contribuire a promuovere sinergie tra produzione agricola, biodiversità e fornitura di servizi ecosistemici di rilevanza locale, regionale e globale.

CRPA Soc.Cons.p.A partner del progetto, gestisce uno dei 20 "progetti pilota" chiamati AURORA Farms, dove vengono testati e dimostrati le buone pratiche per la produzione di foraggi per la produzione di Parmigiano Reggiano di montagna.

Il parere degli attori della filiera è necessario per consolidare i risultati del progetto Radiant, per questo motivo è stato organizzato un focus group per conoscere le aspettative, punti critici, opinioni e discutere insieme alcuni aspetti utili per la produzione di foraggio nell'ambito della filiera del Parmigiano Reggiano di montagna.

Partecipazione su invito: è gradita la [registrazione](#)

CREATOR WORKSHOP SESSIONE CONSUMATORI

- 15:00 Registrazione dei partecipanti
- 15.15 Presentazione del workshop e del progetto Radiant
Elena Bortolazzo – Anna Garavaldi CRPA
Simone Piras – The James Hutton Institute (UK)
- 15.30 Focus group
Simone Piras – The James Hutton Institute (UK)
- 15.40 *Indagine tramite questionario*
- 16.00 *Discussione e focus group*

PROJECT

RADIANT CREATOR WORKSHOP SESSIONE AGRICOLTORI PROGRAM

20 Settembre 2024

Castello di Sarzano, Casina (RE), Italia

Via G. Graziani 1 – Sarzano – Casina (RE)

[44°31'01.25"N 10°29'25.83"E](https://www.google.com/maps/place/44°31'01.25\)

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Partecipazione su invito: è gradita la [registrazione](#)

CREATOR WORKSHOP SESSIONE AGRICOLTORI

- | | |
|-------|---|
| 10.00 | Registrazione dei partecipanti |
| 10.15 | Presentazione del progetto Radiant
<i>Elena Bortolazzo – CRPA scpa</i> |
| 10.30 | Presentazione dell'attività e focus group
<i>Simone Piras – The James Hutton Institute (UK)</i> |
| 12.00 | Visita al campo di confronto varietale di erba medica seminato nell'ambito del progetto Radiant
<i>Fabrizio Ruozzi – CRPA scpa</i> |
| 13.00 | Chiusura dei lavori e pranzo |

Nel pomeriggio siete invitati a partecipare a un demo-event del progetto Climate Farm Demo dedicato all'agricoltura conservativa nelle aziende di montagna per il recupero produttivo dei prati di montagna.

